

RECREATIONAL FISHERIES IN EUROPE AND ROMANIA

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Abstract

This paper is a synthesis of information on recreational fishing in Europe and Romania. In recent years, this type of fishing has become increasingly important in the European Union, and the number of recreational fishermen has increased considerably.

Although the economic and social benefits at a global level are large and the ecological impact on some fish stocks can be considerable, it is necessary that the management in which recreational fishing is carried out is also sustainable. The purpose of this paper is to present the current state of recreational fishing in the EU and in our country.

Introduction

Recreational fishing is the catching of fish for personal, non-commercial purposes, for pleasure, sport or cultural tradition.

Recreational fishing is an important recreational activity with positive social, economic, and environmental effects.

In developed countries, 1 in 10 people fish for pleasure, which represents at least 220 million recreational fishers worldwide (over 5 times more than the number of commercial fishers [14]). It is estimated that ~11% of the total global fish catch comes from recreational fishing, approximately 10 - 12 million tons/year, most of it from inland waters [7].

The economic contribution of recreational fishing is enormous: over 190 billion USD/year and over 900000 direct jobs [3].

Recreational fishing is more developed in countries with coastal areas (USA, Canada, Europe) and in island areas, with reefs, etc.

Recreational fishing is concentrated mainly in the temperate regions of the Northern Hemisphere, in economically developed countries [2], [14], [8].

In many freshwater ecosystems in the Northern Hemisphere, recreational fisheries extract more biomass annually than local commercial fisheries [1]. Currently, recreational fishing is practiced by a large number of people all over the world, being the predominant or even sole user of freshwater fishery resources in developed countries [6].

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Materials and Methods

The work has a descriptive-analytical and comparative character, based on the critical analysis of scientific, legislative, and statistical sources relating to recreational fishing in Europe and Romania.

Methods of documentary analysis, bibliographic synthesis, international comparison, and processing of official data from specialized institutions ([14], [16], [15], [10], [13]) were used.

Also, for our country, official data published by NAFA were used (activity reports, annual orders on the regulation of fishing effort ([19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33])).

Thus, we identified, selected, and interpreted the scientific papers and technical reports relevant to recreational fishing at the European and national level. Then, we compared the relevant data at the level of European countries and Romania.

The lack of complete databases on recreational catches and effort at the national level (Romania) required the use of official estimates publicly communicated by NAFA and data derived from FAO and ICES reports [14], [16].

In the comparative analysis of recreational fishing at the European level, the indicator total number of participants in recreational fishing was used, according to the methodology of FAO (2022), ICES WGRFS (2022), and Hyder et al. (2018).

This indicator reflects the total number of people who practice fishing at least once a year, regardless of holding an active permit. The choice of this unit allows international comparability between countries with different licensing and reporting systems.

Data on licenses are incomplete and uneven. Not all countries in Europe have a single licensing system. Thus:

- In Germany, France, and Poland, licenses are multiple (regional, federal, private);
- In the Netherlands, Sweden, and Norway, recreational fishing in public waters does not require a license;
- In the United Kingdom, the system is mixed: only freshwater fishing is licensed.

Therefore, the number of licenses cannot be directly compared; only the estimated number of participants.

Results and Discussions

Current state of recreational fishing in the EU

Recreational fishing is defined by the European Commission (DG MARE) as: “the taking or attempting to take of living aquatic organisms for non-commercial purposes by natural persons using authorised gear in marine or inland waters of the EU”.

It is regulated separately from commercial fishing, but is considered part of the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), where it has an impact on commercial stocks.

According to ICES WGRFS (Working Group on Recreational Fisheries Surveys, 2022), there are ~25 million recreational fishermen in the EU.

Total annual catches from recreational fishing are estimated at 165000 - 200000 tonnes (marine + inland waters).

Approximately 80% of recreational catches come from inland waters (lakes, rivers, ponds).

The direct economic value exceeds €10 billion per year, and the indirect one (equipment, tourism, services) exceeds €25 billion.

Depending on the region, we have different characteristics of fishing, as follows:

- *Northern Europe* (Scandinavia, Germany, Netherlands), the dominant species in recreational fishing are: pike, perch, and salmon. Here, the catch-and-release system is predominant (>60%).
- *Central Europe* (France, Poland, the Czech Republic, Romania), the predominant recreational fishing is in inland waters. There are numerous national clubs and associations with an emphasis on local lake management.
- *Southern Europe* (Italy, Spain, Greece, Portugal) marine fishing is well developed; many licenses for coastal fishing and charter fishing (fishing trips led by professional people).
- *North Sea & Atlantic* - significant marine recreational fishing for cod, sea bass, plaice.
- *Mediterranean Sea and Black Sea Combined* fishing (recreation + subsistence); growing, with FAO-GFCM projects for joint regulation.

After a synthesis of several sources, we have for each country an estimated number of fishermen shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Number of recreational fishermen in the member countries of the European Union (2022)

<i>Country</i>	<i>Estimated_anglers</i>
Norway	1100000
Sweden	1890000
Finland	1400000
Denmark	885000
Iceland	83600
United Kingdom	4739000
Ireland	459000
Germany	6656000
Netherlands	1062000
Belgium	292500
France	3395000
Spain	1425000
Portugal	360500
Italy	1475000
Switzerland	704000
Austria	591500
Poland	3770000
Czechia	749000
Slovakia	297000
Hungary	576000
Romania	955000
Bulgaria	272000

Greece	312000
Croatia	280000
Slovenia	136500
Serbia	374000
Bosnia and Herzegovina	181500
Montenegro	36000
Albania	126000
North Macedonia	105000
Lithuania	224000
Latvia	171000
Estonia	154000
Luxembourg	26000
Malta	18200
Cyprus	41400

Source: The data presented is a synthesis based on estimates from Hyder et al. (2018), ICES (2022), FAO (2020), Arlinghaus et al. (2015, 2021), GFCM-FAO (2022), and EAA (2019), on participation in recreational fisheries in Europe.

As can be seen in Figure 1, the countries with the highest estimated number of recreational fishermen are Germany, the United Kingdom, Poland, and France.

However, as a percentage of the total population in Finland, 25% of the country's population are recreational fishermen, followed by Iceland 22% and Norway, 20% (figure 2).

According to statistical data, Romania has a significant number of recreational fishermen (955000), which represents 5% of the country's population.

Figure 1. Estimated number of recreational fishermen in European countries

Figure 2. Percentage of recreational fishermen (relative to the total population of the country)

Recreational fishing in Romania

According to national regulations, recreational fishing means fishing carried out with an angle or fishing rod, for recreational purposes, based on a nominal permit issued by the administrator of living aquatic resources and released by him or by recreational fishing associations to their members, as the case may be.

In Romania, there are two public entities with responsibilities regarding the management of living aquatic resources existing in natural fish habitats, as follows:

- *The National Agency for Fisheries and Aquaculture (NAFA)*, which manages living aquatic resources existing in natural fish habitats in inland waters (except the Danube Delta Reserve) and the Black Sea;
- *The Administration of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve (ADDDBR)*, which manages living aquatic resources in the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve.
- The sole authority recognized by the European Commission for coordinating control activities, collecting and certifying information on fishing activities, and ensuring their transmission to the Commission is the National Agency for Fisheries and Aquaculture (NAFA).

The right to fish for recreational purposes in the natural fish habitats in Romania, under the administration of NAFA, is granted based on a nominal permit, issued annually by the administrator of the aquatic resource, without charging fees or charges, as follows:

- directly to fishermen for the Danube River with its branches, the Black Sea, and for natural fish habitats not contracted by recreational fishermen associations;
- through legally established recreational fishermen associations, which have concluded with NAFA, for a period of 10 years, contracts for the use of aquatic resources for all other categories of natural fish habitats.

In Romania, recreational fishing is legal on the Danube, in the Danube Delta, in natural and reservoir lakes (Snagov, Biczaz, Izvorul Muntelui, Siriu), and in the large rivers (Olt, Mureș, Siret).

There is also marine recreational fishing, but its activity is limited mainly to species such as turbot, horse mackerel, and bream.

In natural inland habitats, the target species are: carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), prussian carp (*Carassius gibelio*), northern pike (*Esox lucius*), pike-perch (*Sander lucioperca*), and European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*).

To ensure control of the quantities fished for recreational purposes and to reduce the pressure exerted on the fishery resources in the natural environment, the total allowable catch (TAC) is regulated annually by order of the Minister of Agriculture.

Thus, quotas are allocated annually for recreational fishing in inland waters (especially the Danube and the Prut River).

For the Black Sea, TACs are mainly linked to the commercial fishing opportunities established annually at the EU level (e.g., Regulation (EU) 259/2024), and there is no explicit breakdown for recreational fishing. Marine recreational fishing in Romania is regulated mainly through daily limits and prohibitions, not through dedicated TACs.

The total allowable catch (TAC) for the period 2010 - 2025 for recreational fishing was established by MARD Orders, regarding the approval of the measures regulating fishing effort and fishing quotas, and is presented as follows:

Table 2. TACs and fishing effort for recreational fisheries are regulated annually by ministerial order

Year of issuance of the ministerial order	Total allowable catch TAC (t)			Number of recreational fishermen	
	<i>Danube River</i>	<i>Prut River</i>	<i>Reservoirs on the Olt River</i>	<i>Danube River</i>	<i>Prut River</i>
2010	183.5			700	36700
2011	176	45		700	32200
2012	176	57		700	32200
2013	169	57			32200
2014	145	47,4			32200
2015	141.4	33.9			9000
2016	146.9	33.9			9000
2017	146.9	25.9	97.65		
2018	146.9	25.9	101.25		
2019	146.9	25.9			
2020	146.9	25.9			
2022	148	28			
2023	148	28			
2024	148	28			
2025	148	28			

Data are extracted from the Annual Fishing Effort and Quota Regulations Orders

Analyzing the data on the distribution of total allowable catches (TACs) on the Danube and Prut Rivers during the period 2010 - 2025, it is observed that:

- TACs on the Danube River during the period 2010 - 2025 vary between a minimum of 141.4 t and a maximum of 183.5 t.
- TACs on the Prut River during the period 2010 - 2025 vary between a minimum of 25.9 t and a maximum of 57 t (figure 3).

Figure 3. TACs dynamics on the Danube and Prut Rivers (2010 – 2025)

The dynamics of the number of recreational fishermen are shown in Table 3.

For the period 2010 – 2014, we have the fishing effort quantified in the number of recreational fishermen.

Starting from 2016, we have the estimated number of recreational fishing permits issued by NAFA according to the mentioned sources.

Table 3. Estimated number of sport fishing permits issued for the Danube River and non-contracted waters

<i>Year</i>	<i>No. of NAFA permits (≈)</i>	<i>Main source of information</i>
2010	36700	Order No. 19/237 of 27 January 2010
2011	41200	Order No. 999 of March 2, 2011
2012	41200	Order No. 116 of 22 May 2012
2013	41200	Order No. 1318 of May 24, 2013
2014	41200	Order No. 284 of March 27, 2014
2016	52935	Court of Auditors Report [11]
2017	35000	Court of Auditors Report [11]
2018	70000	Court of Auditors Report [11]
2019	163259	Court of Auditors Report [11]
2020	~250000	NAFA estimate according to DCNews interview [18]
2021	~300000	NAFA report 2021 [10]
2022	~345000	NAFA report 2022 [10]
2023	~410000	NAFA press release [9]
2024	~440000	NAFA year-end projection [9]
Minimum	35000	
Maximum	440000	
Average	161978,1429	

The number of recreational fishermen is growing rapidly (Figure 4). The main reason for the increase in the number of permits issued is the increased interest of the population in practicing recreational fishing following the elimination of the permit issuance, combined with the lack of implementation of criteria for granting them that would ensure a balance between the number of permits issued and existing aquatic resources.

Figure 4. Evolution of the number of permits issued by NAFA

In Romania, administrative data provided by NAFA (2024) indicate approximately 440000 active fishermen with a valid permit, but according to international methodology [8], [15], the total annual participation is estimated at approximately 900000 – 1000000 people.

The difference between the two values reflects the distinct reporting methodologies and the lack of a standardized national system for collecting data on recreational effort, a situation common to many countries in the Eastern European region.

Conclusions

Recreational fishing in Romania represents a significant socio-economic activity, with an estimated participation of approximately 900000 - 1000000 people annually, of which 400000 - 450000 hold valid permits issued by NAFA. This level of participation places Romania among the European states with an consolidated tradition in continental recreational fishing.

Official statistical data on recreational effort and catches are fragmented, which limits Romania's integration into the European ICES–WGRFS reporting system. The lack of a unified data collection system (CPUE, reported catches, and fishing effort) makes it difficult to accurately assess the real impact on fishery resources and the economic contribution at the national level.

The legislative and institutional framework is aligned with the principles of the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), but has its own structure based on Law 176/2024 and the annual orders of the MADR/MMAP.

Currently, the regulation of recreational fishing is based more on effort control (through permits, prohibition periods, minimum retention sizes) than on quantitative limits such as TACs, which are only partially applied in the case of the Danube and the Prut rivers.

From an ecological point of view, the impact of recreational fishing is low on a national scale, but can become significant in sensitive habitats (Danube Delta, small lakes, heavily frequented rivers). Modern practices, such as catch and release, restocking with native species, and respecting minimum retention sizes, contribute to the conservation of aquatic biodiversity.

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References

[1] Arlinghaus, R., Cooke, S. J., Lyman, J., Policansky, D., Schwab, A., Suski, C., & Thorstad, E. B. (2007). Understanding the complexity of catch-and-release in recreational fishing: An integrative synthesis of global knowledge from historical, ethical, social, and biological perspectives. *Reviews in Fisheries Science*, 15(1–2), 75–167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10641260601149432>

- [2] Arlinghaus, R., Cooke, S. J., & Cowx, I. G. (2015). Global impact of recreational fisheries. *Science*, 347(6224), 239–243. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa6374>
- [3] Arlinghaus, R., Abbott, J. K., Fenichel, E. P., Carpenter, S. R., Hunt, L. M., Alós, J., Klefoth, T., Cooke, S. J., Hilborn, R., Jensen, O. P., Wilberg, M. J., Post, J. R., & Manfredi, M. J. (2019). Governing the recreational dimension of global fisheries. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(12), 5209–5213. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1902796116>
- [4] Arlinghaus, R., Aas, Ø., Alós, J., Arismendi, I., Bower, S., Carle, S., Czarkowski, T., Freire, K. M. F., Hu, J., Hunt, L. M., Lyach, R., Kapusta, A., Salmi, P., Schwab, A., Tsuboi, J.-i., Trella, M., McPhee, D., Potts, W., Wołos, A., & Yang, Z.-J. (2021). Global participation in and public attitudes toward recreational fishing: International perspectives and developments. *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*, 29(1), 58–95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2020.1795615>
- [5] Arlinghaus, R., Hyder, K., & Strehlow, H. V. (2021). The social and ecological outcomes of recreational fisheries worldwide. *Fish and Fisheries*, 22(6), 1241–1265. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12581>
- [6] Bețiviu, D. (2014). Pescuitul fluvial recreativ în Uniunea Europeană. *Analele Institutului Național de Cercetări Economice*, (1), 80–84. ISBN 978-9975-4326-6-5.
- [7] Cooke, S. J., & Cowx, I. G. (2004). The role of recreational fishing in global fish crises. *Science*, 305(5692), 1958–1959. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1102120>
- [8] Hyder, K., Weltersbach, M. S., Armstrong, M., Ferter, K., Townhill, B., & Strehlow, H. V. (2018). Recreational sea fishing in Europe in a global context. *Fish and Fisheries*, 19(2), 225–243. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12251>

Institutional Reports and Documents

- [9] ANPA. (2023 – 2024). Comunicate de presă. Agenția Națională pentru Pescuit și Acvacultură.
- [10] ANPA – Rapoarte de activitate (2020 - 2024).
- [11] Curtea de Conturi. (2020). Raport public privind performanța ANPA (2016–2019). București: Curtea de Conturi a României.
- [12] European Anglers Alliance (EAA). (2019). The economic value of recreational fisheries in the European Union. Brussels: European Anglers Alliance. <https://www.eaa-europe.org/>
- [13] European Commission, DG MARE. (2023). Recreational fisheries management in the EU. Brussels: European Commission.
- [14] FAO. (2020). The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020: Sustainability in action. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9229en>
- [15] GFCM–FAO. (2022). Recreational fisheries in the Mediterranean and Black Sea. Rome: General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean, FAO. <https://www.fao.org/gfcm>
- [16] ICES. (2022). Report of the Working Group on Recreational Fisheries Surveys (WGRFS 2022). Copenhagen: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea. <https://ices.dk/sites/pub/Publication%20Reports>

Press articles

- [17] Adevărul. (n.d.). [Articole privind pescuitul recreativ, citând datele ANPA și MADR].
- [18] DCNews. (n.d.). [Articole privind pescuitul recreativ, citând datele ANPA și MADR].

Normative acts

- [19] Order No. 19/237/2010 on the approval of the measures regulating fishing effort and fishing quotas for 2010.
- [20] Order No. 999/2011 on the approval of the measures regulating fishing effort and fishing quotas for 2011, by species and areas.
- [21] Order No. 116/2012 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and the fishing quotas allocated for 2012.
- [22] Order No. 1318/2013 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and the fishing quotas allocated for 2013.
- [23] Order No. 284/2014 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and the fishing quotas allocated for 2014, by species and areas.
- [24] Order No. 165/2015 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and the fishing quotas allocated for 2015, by species and areas.
- [25] Order No. 284/613/2015 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and the fishing quotas allocated for 2016, by species and areas.
- [26] Order No. 13/142/2017 approving measures to regulate fishing effort and allocation of fishing quotas for 2017 on species and areas. Monitorul Oficial al României, Nr. 141/24.02.2017.

[27] Order No. 546/352/2018 approving measures to regulate fishing effort and allocation of fishing quotas for 2018 on species and areas.

[28] Order No. 243/354/2019 approving measures to regulate fishing effort and quotas allocated for 2019, by species and areas.

[29] Order No. 124/1159/2020 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and the fishing quotas allocated for 2020, by species and areas.

[30] Order No. 45/558/2022 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and the fishing quotas allocated for the year 2022, by species and areas.

[31] Order No. 45/539/2023 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and fishing quotas allocated for 2023, by species and areas.

[32] Order No. 75/874/2024 on the approval of the measures regulating the fishing effort and fishing quotas allocated for 2024, by species and areas.

[33] Order No. 52/17 February 2025 on the approval of the measures regulating fishing effort and fishing quotas allocated annually, by species and areas.